

EDITORIAL QUALITY

in Diamond Open Access publishing

Providing clear and transparent editorial information on a journal's website ensures the quality and trustworthiness of published research.

Here are seven key elements a journal should display to demonstrate its commitment to rigorous evaluation, ethical standards, and publication quality, building trust among authors, readers, and other users.

Mission and scope

- Outline the publication's aims, scope, and target audience.
- State the frequency of publication and ensure publication dates reflect when content is available online.

- Declare that the journal is Diamond Open Access (no mandatory fees for authors).
- If Voluntary Author Contributions (VAC) is an option, it must be clear that there is no obligation to do so.

Open Access Policy

Author Guidelines

Provide clear guidelines on the submission process, including the languages in which manuscripts can be submitted, article types accepted, and any formatting requirements, stylesheets or templates to be used.

- Describe the peer-review procedure, including:
- Timeframe and stages of review
 - Who is involved at what stage of the process
 - How decisions are made and by whom.

Evaluation processes

Editorial policies

- Clearly outline policies on:
 - Authorship and contributorship.
 - Handling complaints, appeals, conflicts of interest.
 - Allegations of research misconduct.
- Follow industry standards (e.g., COPE guidelines).

- Address key issues like:
 - Text and data mining permissions.
 - Open repositories and content sharing.
 - Archiving and preservation of published content.
- Explain how publishing infrastructure is maintained, backed up, and protected.

Additional policies

Tips

- Information should be written clearly and be jargon free
- All policy and procedure details should be fully described and transparent
- Information should be easy to find by including it in relevant menus and cross linking between sections.
- External website review can help identify areas for improved transparency